

Perceived Parental Image in Paintings of Children with Moderate Mental Disability

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 11, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 02 , 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Parental Image, Children Paintings, Children with Mental Disability</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4410927</p>	<p><i>Children of moderate mental disability form their own images of their parents. The purpose of this study is to explore parental image which is perceived in children with moderate mental disability in Shobak region through the projection of paintings that they create. The sample of the study consisted of four children (2 males, 2 females) with moderate mental disability in the ages between (9-10) years, while their mental age is (5-6) years. Family painting and children paintings context analysis card were used as data collection tool. The results of the analysis showed that the relations between all children and their parents and between parents themselves are deteriorated. This reflects family disintegration, and all the images reflected inability to imagine better future in all cases for parents and children, except for the image of (Mohamed) who aspired to alleviate his future pressure and to have future better than his past with understanding of inability to achieve this wish. There appeared to be apparent conflict between children in the role of father and mother. Some of them believe that the father is a source of threat and punishment, while the mother is not. Others believe that mother is a source of threat and punishment, and some of them believe both parents are so. It was noted that the element of color in all paintings doesn't exist. This indicates emotional gap that children suffer, and sometimes reflects inclination to hate society.</i></p>

1. Introduction

Good family is the medium where children strike balance between need to communication and need to independence in their relations with others. Unsound families have special interactions and communications, and often fail to direct child to strike this balance [1]. Childhood touches an important humanitarian sense as category of children doesn't and can't protect itself or obtain its rights. Role of parents appears in this point; they are vested with the duty of satisfying the various physical, mental, emotional and social needs of children [2].

Adults express their feelings, emotions and needs by explicit verbal and oral methods, and indirect methods that are subconsciously transformed from a form to another. However, the method of expression of those feelings is different in children, particularly those whose language capacities don't quality them to accurately express their feelings and needs that they desire to meet. Consequently, art, painting and coloring in the stage of childhood is an important and effective means of understanding the latent feelings, motivations and tendencies of children [3].

Painting expands the children capacities of analysis and observation, and increases child's self-confidence and make him capable of accepting others and gaining experiences that help him create self-concept [4]. In this stage, children paintings are characterized by realism because child is more adherent to nature as a result of growth of his perception and increase of experience. Rohner [5], author of the theory of parental acceptance/ rejection, notes that individual's perception of parent warmth gets him to feel his value and importance, and he becomes more capable of facing problems, while individual's perception of the forms of parental rejection causes his feeling of insecurity, dependency and inefficiency. This negative theory extends from himself to the world and others. He sees the world as unsafe and threatening place, so child is always in a state of withdrawal, anticipation, and inclination to aggressive behavior [6].

Art practices have positive effect on individuals with special needs in terms of application of mental operations such as observation, attention, feeling, perception and ability to understand visual information. All this application can be utilized in the various daily life situations. They don't produce paintings like those produced by ordinary child [7]. Therefore, children with special needs, particularly deaf and children with mental disability, must use projection paintings. Painting for them is a very favorable means to control the problem of oral communication.

Psychological Researchers and therapists turned to use paintings as means by which patients who are not good at speaking the spoken language, because painting is a language that can build channel of

communication between patient and therapist to exchange ideas and meanings between them and to explore the internal conflicts of patients [8].

Study Problem:

Educators unanimously agree that painting is a nonverbal diagnostic means that help in diagnosis of some characteristics because it is an easy, cost-efficient and favorable means for children, particularly children with mental disabilities. Although painting methods are diverse, painting human figure is the most common subject in children painting [9]. Koppitz [10] states that painting of human figure is a variable projection tool for diagnosis of psychological orders and assessment of children with emotional problems.

In this study, children paintings are chosen as means for identification of parental image in children with mental disabilities because paintings proved to be a form of emotional release and reflection of their feelings towards themselves and towards others. Therefore, we can identify whether or not children with mental disabilities suffer parental maltreatment. The problem of this study was crystallized in the following question:

- How children with mental disability see the parental image as illustrated by their paintings?

Research Objectives:

The main aim of this study is to explore the perceived parental image in the paintings of children with moderate mental disability according to their paintings.

Research Significance:

Significance of the study derives from importance and specificity of the category, which is examined by the study; being children with mental disability and the means for exploring their concerns and problems that they encounter. Practically, analysis of children paintings is a scientific medium that highlights the negative psychological feelings of children. If such feelings are neglected by society, they will lead later to increase of the phenomena that destroy societies, and exploration of their positive feelings that, if cared for and developed, will lead to development and sound building of societies. Therefore, early exploration of those feelings will help us set recommendations to help those in charge of childcare reach sound mental health.

Theoretical Framework:

Painting as a means of projection tests doesn't depend on the correct or false answers. Children is left in painting in privacy to logically express what he sees to determine the personality track by painting [11]. Moreover, it is a mirror that reflects the child's values and tendencies towards the family members around him [12]. Children paintings are free planning by which they express on whatever surface, from their early holding of pen until they reach the stage of adulthood [13]. It is "Intentional recall and attempt for expression of mental image that child infers and deals with. Free painting derives its roots from the child's emotion and is nourished by visual, tactile, audio and verbal information, facts and perceptions that children gains from his environment [14].

Al Quraiti [11] presented definition of children free painting as "Paintings which are haphazardly produced by child automatically in response to internal desire, to achieve a certain idea, or unconsciously when tools that he applies in expression or the time to be taken in this expression. Face may be the most significant part of the body in young children. Social communication is made and satisfaction is realized by face. By observation of facial expressions, child learns that there are events that will take place and takes young children paintings on head and face, followed in importance by limbs where social communication is achieved and environment is approached and controlled [15]. Children unconsciously paint what they know, not what they see; that is, they express by painting what they know, not what they see. Children paintings express the concepts in their minds [16].

There are many theories that interpret children paintings. We will focus in this study on the analytical theory, which dictates that children paintings express desires and needs that exist in the unconscious, which are considered in the analytical perspective to be messages directed to others to credibly and faithfully illustrate the deep personalities of their senders. Drawn figures are visual symbols with certain psychological significance because of their close relation to the latent unconscious side of the individual's personality, and the problems and difficulties that he suffers [14]. Freud emphasizes that art comes after dreams as a means for identification of depths [17].

Advocates of analytical curve assign considerable importance in investigation of paintings to availing full freedom to client. When the children or adult, to atomically, explicitly and fully express his feelings, emotions and internal world without obstructing him by certain directions or restricting him by specific performance skills with observation of his behavior during the art expression. Such will be by regular, accurate observation, and recording their results, then studying its formal codes, combing, and interpreting them within the framework of information, which is gathered on the client's case [11]. Horney notes that the individual who

doesn't feel love and respect of parents in the early years of childhood suppresses the feeling of hatred and enmity towards his parents and other persons around him, and his self-confidence is shaken, which leads to personal disorder. Self is reflection of effective person [18].

There are many factors affect children paintings. These factors can be summarized as follows:

- A. Gender: There are differences between paintings of girls and boys. Those differences appear in early period from approximately the age of six, and become more distinguished over years. Girls' paintings reflect inclination to painting persons with whole face more than boys who draw face portraits.
- B. Intelligence: Child with mental disability paints human according to child's disability. This is different from the painting of mentally ordinary or superior child. This was reflected by "Godanf" Scale of man painting. He assured the fact that by increase of mental maturity of child details contained in his painting increase, and painting becomes more consistent [13].
- C. Age: (Bo, et al., 2008) noted that young children paintings are different from adult children paintings, and children paintings are different from those of adults, and indicated the effect of child's age on his ability of painting.
- D. Environment: Children reflect in their paintings the social, political and economic background of children. Accordingly, paintings of children who suffer poverty and oppression are immersed in the reality of daily suffering. Lim & Slaughter [19] emphasized the role of environment in affecting children painting by brief report on children paintings in description of man, and he highlighted the importance of having interesting and encouraging stimuli to be provided to child before beginning of painting. There must be socio-environmental stimuli to help children practice painting.

If paintings are important in study of mental intelligence and maturity of children, they are more feasible in study of their personalities and identification of their latent feelings and diagnosis of their disorders.

Kauffman & Hallahan [16] reckoned set of properties that characterize the paintings of children with mental disabilities, including significant tendency to mechanism and slow movement from a stage to another. Tendency to setback and return to a stage that has been previously planned, and dispersion of ideas and movement from an idea to another without introduction appear. In addition, some children with mental disabilities have extraordinary ability of visual remembrance. Some children with mental disability show desire to represent their ideas as a whole. Those children prefer the paintings on which the same movements are repeated.

Literatures Review:

Study of Ahmad (2017) aimed at identification of the painting characteristics of slow learning children in Babel Governorate, Iraq. Results showed that majority of children paint depending on the solid line. Line direction varied from a student to another. They also depended on color when they painted the external border and it varied inside. In addition, figure details were litter and scattered distribution feature prevailed.

Study of Hameed (2015) aimed at identification of the properties of formal perception in the paintings of children with special needs and normal children in Iraq. The research sample was (40) children divided into (20) children with special needs and (20) normal children. The researcher used painting analysis form prepared by (Samya Al-Rashed) for the stage of formal perception. Results showed that there are differences in the properties of formal perception between children with special needs and normal children.

Al Qaisi (2011) conducted study that aimed at diagnosing the phenomenon of social isolation of children who lost their father as compared to children who did not lose their father. The study used projection painting done by children. Results showed that children who lost their father feel social isolation more than children who did not lose their father in clear ratios.

Study Methodology:

Study Sample: Sample of the study consisted of four children (2 males and 2 females) with moderate mental disability in Al-Dhiaa Center for Children with special needs in Al Shoubak Region in the Southern Jordan in ages (9-10) years old. Concerning mental age, it is between (5-6) years old. Conditions and specifications of the sample of the study can be defined as follows:

1. Sample of the study consisted of child of both genders (males and females).
2. The sample did not contain any type of other disabilities. It was limited to moderate mental disability.
3. Convergence of socio-economic and cultural status of the families of children of the sample of the study.
4. Children whose families have more than one case of mental disability were excluded.
5. Children of divorced and orphans were excluded.

Methodology of the study: Descriptive analytical methodology was used by analysis of the significance of paintings in children with moderate mental disability.

Instruments of the study: Family painting test and children painting context analysis card were used to detect parental concept. These were prepared by the researchers and designed after review of several painting analysis cards, including: painting analysis list (Othman, 1979). Children painting context analysis form on their perceptions about violence (Moustafa, 2010). In the study of paintings, the researchers depended on the following indicators: (sizes- positions- head, eyes, mouth, ears)- limbs (arms and feet)- (movement- highlighting). Each of them was translated into several figures that express how dimension exists in the child's painting.

Analytical side of the study:

Child No (1) Ramez

Overall impression about the painting: The general shape of painting shows that there are no considerable activities between the group members (parents- child), which shows family disintegration and disintegration of satisfying relations between (child, father, mother). As a result, child suffers deformed inflation of body image, including deformed inflation of self-image as replacement side of child's feeling of inferiority.

Relative sizes of painted figures: Big and dominating size is that of child, and small size is that of mother. Deformed and incomplete figure is that of (father), which reflects fragmentation of parental image and feeling of inferiority towards them, particularly (father).

Positions of figures on the area of painting paper: Asymmetry of family size appeared either by distance or displacement at the top of page. Such shows that there are difficulties of communication or convergence with the persons who are important for him (father and mother), in addition to his feeling of isolation from mother with shocking barriers in the child's relation with mother (pavement) that wasn't felt with father who represents for him a source of threat and punishment (stick).

Head: The painting appeared to be with deformed features whether in relation to (children or parents), particularly loss of important part of the head which is "ears". This proves lack of communication, dialogue and intimate relation between the child and his parents. However, the biggest part of the child's head inclined more to mother's status and position, which means ability of both of them (mother and child) to understand the other more than understanding father.

The two samples were withdrawn by the child with the same dimension, which reflects rejection of communication with the external world and avoidance of seeing painful visual stimuli; that is, external environment of parents (as perceived by child) appeared to be unpleasing and unsatisfying, and source of anxiety, disturbance and rejection.

Arms: They completely disappeared from painting, which means that child needs parental help with feeling of lack of efficiency and inability of communication, in addition to parents' inability to give and contribute.

Movement: It completely disappeared in the image and silence and rigidity dominated over the movement and communication of parents with child whether near to distance or by arms, which means violation and tension of the intimate emotional relation.

Highlighting: Child inclines to highlight the whole body, which reflects inconsistency, aggression and need to sympathy and tender with those around him (parents), in addition to his feeling of anxiety and mouth and moral dissatisfaction.

Child (2) Mohamed

Overall impression about painting: That reflects family disintegration and break of relations between (father-mother) (parents- child) with the child's ambition for better position in the future, although child feels that this wish is impossible to realize (vertical line above the child and painting of parents in fully separate image from that of child).

Concerning image of father and mother: They were completely ignored in the first painting, and were put in very pale form in the other painting. In addition to their painting in rod-shaped form, distant from each other, which proves marginalization of their image whether in life with each other or with the child himself, and low level of physical and psychological energy. Child's resort to rod-shaped people often proves that child seeks safety and security from both of them and wants to avoid risks in the future. That is, acceptance of child as he is with his health conditions (mental disability).

Concerning the personal positions in the space of painting paper: The painting appeared to be similar to child's size but incomplete. That proves feeling of inferiority towards the world, without any significant reaction from the part of the child with this world. However, he aims at alleviating isolation in the future (the weak line above head) which is completely different from the past (multidimensional pavement).

Head: Head appeared to be symmetrical in side with the body, but it lost important part of it, which is ears. This proves that child refuses dialogue with intimate relation between child and parents, and refuses hearing the directions and instructions delivered to him by parents so child turned to conceal and drop that important part of the head, in addition to separation and alienation of parents in space of the image and realization of them in separate image.

Samples: They appeared to be deformed and interfering with the interference of pupil, which proves that the child has distorted vision of the external world. This feeling was applied to an important part of head, which is eye, which is a source of communication with the external world.

Mouth: Mouth appeared to be open and hollow without any features, which means that language of dialogue almost does not exist or is not understandable, in addition to the fact that mouth is the source of satisfaction. Therefore, child himself feels to be suffering material deprivation and emotional deprivation. Children who often suffer verbal offense draw big open mouth as if they are always ready to be cut or devoured by others.

Limbs (arms and feet): They child has dropped them, meaning that language of communication and intimacy between the child and external environment represented in (father- mother) almost does not exist. This proves that child is very isolated whether in verbal, hand or feet communication, which is confirmed by this barrier and enclosure that child established around himself separately, not only from parents, but also from the world as a whole.

Child (3) Rawan

Overall impression of painting: General shape of painting shows that child is richer in terms of her feeling and sense with her family members, because of convergence and understanding among parents, in addition to the fact that they are extrovert, easy and appealing persons. However, in the meantime, they suffer the feeling of alienation and isolation from the other family members, which forces her to approach an important person for her. Her grandmother may also suffer considerable distortion of her personality.

Similarity between painted figures: All family members appeared to be completely similar in terms of shape, which reflects impersonation and autism showed by child with her family members, which controls the competitive desires and equality between them.

Position of persons in the space of paper: Persons in the space of paper are distant, except for parents, which means that child suffers inability to achieve her objectives of communication with her family members. Putting parents at the bottom of paper proves lack of feeling of security, although she struggles to achieve stability and safety with them.

Movement in painting: Movement decreases and rigidity, silence and distance increases with all family members, except for communication and convergence among parents, which means that child feels alienation among her family members. However, parents' communication with each other makes the child more wishing in her feeling of safety and security.

Head: There appeared to be mismatch of head size between (father- mother- child) that ranged between (round-squared- normal) that reflects disorder of perception and thinking in all persons, in addition to dropping (ears) in all figures. This reflects language of silent dialogue, because no one has the ability to hear the other. Ears are the source of communication with the external world, and parties of dialogue lose this communication. Mouth in all images and persons appeared to be more inclined to smiling, which reflects low intensity of dialogue and clear extroversion and appeal of all parties of dialogue (**father- mother- children**). However, communication and intimacy appeared to be weak and distant in all family members, except for parents.

Eyes: These are key members of the sensory system and receipt of stimuli and communication with the external world. They ranged between (hollow above the head without pupil and its position with single dimension). This proves rejection of communication with the external world, and lack of optimistic future vision, and that reason for this is shame and shyness of family because of the child's condition (mental disability). In addition, children who feel that they are observed or controlled often draw big eyes with close suspicious looks. Significance of closed eyes is evidence of painful vision.

Limbs (arms and feet): Arms appeared (in spite of their existence) appeared in the two short paintings not connected and inconsistent with body size and feet, which reflects desire of communication with the environment and others or desire of help and interaction and short hands reflect the feelings related to insecurity, helplessness and anxiety. Child completely feels loss of all types of communication whether by dialogue, intimacy or communication with each other, and that she is in need to support of family members, particularly parents to her.

Child (4) Assil

Overall impression about painting: In the general shape of both paintings, the perceived image of child towards father and mother appears, and the key representation of it is inconsistency between them. Mother is considered to be the source of anxiety, disturbance and noise with feeling of inferiority towards the person of father, the child wishes him to have more positive role in this. In addition, there are feelings of guilt that the child will have towards her mother because of her latent aggressive desire, which child tries hard to conceal and control in an attempt to achieve part of the intimate and positive feelings of mother in order to get rid of dual feelings towards her.

Use of abnormal methods of person painting: Child painted father and mother in rod shape for their limbs, which means strong desire of child to feel security and her desire to avoid risks. The child inclines to conceal all her negative feelings towards parents. In addition, she painted her mother more than 15 degree inclined from the vertical posture, which gives impression of imbalance from mother and lack of feeling of security by the child. However, the child suffers dual feelings towards her mother; between her concerns about mother's domination and instinct love towards her (heart symbol).

Position of figure in the space of paper: In the first painting, all figures were above the paper of painting. That means small part of the painting paper was used in spite of the overall size of paper such as when child withdraws to corner of it, which means that child needs to feel security and further care and love. It also proves inability to encounter this group and this child's relation to space is relation of fear and hesitation. In the second painting, father and mother appeared to be in the center of paper, which means domination of the scene of distorted relation between parents under strong attention and anxiety of all family members, particularly child.

Erasure in paper: Mother's image of face that was removed and repainted, which reflects severe anxiety and lack of confidence towards mother. In addition, the aggressive desires that are accompanied by feeling of sin and guilt from child towards her mother, who tries to conceal and cover it. That was not met in the position of father who was painted by the child in larger size than father's size. It reflects the child's desire to dominate the position as whole for no hope by the removal that signifies the feeling of conflict of the child's hesitation, ambiguity and lack of feeling of security.

Movement: Movement appeared to be lacking between family members who suffer lack of communication because of loss of all means of communication including ears, hands and feet, excluding father and mother who appeared with rod-shaped feet because of child's desire to avoid their risks; that is, communication among family members is completely distorted.

Concerning head: Head sizes varied between parents and child. However, it showed much details in terms of eyes, ears, mouth and nose, which reflects the child's desire to be more intelligent and capable of achievement. However, this is considered ambition of the child without the child's real ability to achieve this. Mouth appeared to be source of noise and disturbance, particularly in the person of mother who suffers much of loss of good dialogue with abundance of noisy, disturbing dialogue, which is characterized by objection and rejection and may reach screaming. Over emphasis of painting or enlarging of mouth means disorders of languages, speech or dependence on others. Existence of ears in this dialogue is a source of receiving mother's screaming and disturbance of them only.

Eyes: Eyes appeared to be more detailed for the father's person where pupil exists, in addition to painting of mother's eyes that see reality only by her thinking. Mother loses receiving of stimuli and communication with the external world except through her mouth, which represent a source of severe disturbance to child.

Arms: Arms of parents appeared to be rod-shaped with their loss of all family members, which means that child is in conflict between her concerns about parents' punishment or feeling that parents are ineffective or less capable of achievement, and incapable of sound communication with the remaining family.

Overall impression of all children painting

- General shape of painting shows that there are no considerable activities among the group members (**Mother- Child- Father**) which means that there is something to emphasize family disintegration and break of satisfying relations and unpleasing relations among all cases and their parents.
- The relation between parents with each other suffer break and lack of dialogue except for the image of (Assil) who showed distorted dialogue between father and mother, and that mother is a source of domination, hegemony and power with feeling of weakness, scantiness and inferiority of father's role. Image of (Rawan) that showed amputated intimacy between parents who have tolerance and acceptance with each other, except for children.
- Images showed that parents are not able to contribute whether verbally, morally or intimately, except for the image of (Assil) for mother, which proves much verbal noisy and disturbing dialogue, which is more punishing than warm rewarding.
- All images showed inability to imagine a better future in all cases for parents and children, except for the image of (Mohamed) who aspires to alleviate pressure on him in the future, and to have a better future than past with awareness of his inability to realize this wish.
- Overall impression is clear. Family, particularly brothers and sisters (**as perceived by children**), are unable to communicate and to have intimacy between all of them, which is in contradiction to facts, which shall have some convergence between some family members (denial of reality).
- Children dropped their latent desires of equality and positive treatment that children (under study) do not feel, which means that they use the mechanism of (reaction formation) as alternative to their feeling of loss.
- There is apparent conflict between children in the role of father and mother. Some of them believe that father is source of threat and punishment (Ramez), except for mother. Others believe that mother is a

source of threat and punishment (Assil), and some believe that parents do not represent disturbing source of threat and punishment (Rawan), (Mohamed).

- Dual feelings (love- hatred, rejection- acceptance, granting- preventing) towards mother were noted with the accompanying feelings of sin and guilt towards this dualism (Assil).
- It was noted that the element of color did not exist in all paintings, which reflects emotional gap that children suffer, and sometimes reflects inclination to be aggressive to society.

Thinking capacities of the children under study: All children, in spite of their low mental capacities, which do not match their age, appeared to perceive the tragedy that they suffer as a result of mental retardation. They completely perceive parents' rejection of their disability and rejection of that disability. In addition, they perceive that they are source of those problems, tension, anxiety and strong frustration in family because of this disability and rejection of it by their ambient environment, which was negatively reflected on their feelings that flare with negativity, frustration, egocentrism and self-denial.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Children embodied in images their latent desires of equality and positive treatment that they don't feel which means that they use (reaction formation) mechanism as alternative to their feeling of loss, in addition to inability of parents to contribution, whether verbal or moral, or intimacy. It was observed that there are dual feelings towards mother in terms of (love-hatred, refusal-acceptance, granting- preventing) and the accompanying feelings of guilt and sin towards this dualism. Based on the findings, the following are recommended:

- 1- Qualifying specialized female teachers in the field of painting for children with mental disability.
- 2- Providing children with mental disability the opportunities and encouragement, which are required for use of painting as a means of expression of themselves and their needs.
- 3- Conducting tracking studies of the various stages of painting as compared to the age groups of children with mental disabilities.

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